

Study of Flow Field at Impeller Exit of a Centrifugal Compressor

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ABSTRACT: This paper presents a numerical investigation of the effects of tip clearance on the performance and flow field in a centrifugal compressor. This study focuses in particular on the tip clearance at the tip of the blade and location of the wake. This investigation deals with performance improvement of a centrifugal compressor by partial shroud placed near the rotor blade tip tested in the flow simulations. Computational study of centrifugal compressor is carried out with finite volume method upwind scheme using ANSYS-CFX software. Centrifugal compressor impeller with three values of clearances i.e. 2.2%, 5.1% and 7.9% of blade height at trailing edge are examined at four flow coefficients 0.12, 0.18, 0.28 and 0.34. The effect of tip clearance on total impeller efficiency, work input coefficient, tangential velocity and radial velocity from inlet to outlet of the compressor are analyzed. The drop in static pressure coefficient and total pressure coefficient with increase in tip clearance is found to be high at the tip of the blade due to high pressure fluid leakage at the tip of the blade. Although the performance improved for low tip clearances, a low tip clearance at the tip of the trailing edge improved the compressor performance more significantly than a lower tip clearance at the leading edge.

Keywords: Centrifugal compressor, partial shrouds and tip clearance.

1. INTRODUCTION

The centrifugal compressors have a wide range of applications especially for power plants for small aircraft and helicopters, in process industries, compression of gases and vapours, because they can provide high-pressure ratios and large operating ranges with relatively high efficiencies. Centrifugal compressors are used primarily for their suitability for handling small volume flows, but other advantages include a shorter length than an equivalent axial flow compressor, less susceptibility to loss of performance by buildup of deposits on the blade surfaces and their suitability to operate over a wide range of mass flow. A better understanding of the flow mechanism underlying the secondary flow fields inside compressors is essential for the design of centrifugal compressors with improved performance and extended operational ranges [1]. The main flow in centrifugal compressors is sensitive to secondary flows generated by the channel curvature as well as the centrifugal and Coriolis forces. In un-shrouded impellers, the tip clearance flow significantly affects the performance and flow field because it causes pressure losses over the tip clearance and strengthens the secondary flows. The influence of the tip clearance flow on the performance and flow structure in centrifugal compressors has been studied by many researchers [4–12]. In previous studies, it was found that the swirling flows and vortex motions within un-shrouded impellers are sensitive to the tip clearance flow. Consequently, these flows produce high losses and degrade performance if the tip clearance is large. The main objective of this work is to numerically investigate the effects of various tip clearance specifications on the performance and flow field in a centrifugal compressor, particularly focusing on the tip region. Numerical simulations were conducted for a centrifugal compressor impellers in which the different tip clearances for different flow coefficients.

2. COMPUTATIONAL METHODOLOGY

The design details of the impeller which is used in the present investigation are given below:

Total pressure rise, Δp :	300 mm WG
Volume flow rate, V :	1.12 m ³ /s
Speed of rotation, N :	2000 rpm
Shape number, N_{sh} :	0.092
No. of rotor blades, Z :	16
Inducer hub diameter, d_{1h} :	160 mm
Inducer tip diameter, d_{1t} :	300 mm
Rotor tip diameter, d_2 :	500 mm
Blade height at the exit, h_2 :	34.74 mm
Blade angle at inducer tip, β_{1t} :	35°
Blade angle inducer hub, β_{1h} :	53°
Blade angle at exit, β_2 : (a) At hub:75°, (b) At mean section:90°, (c) At tip: 105°	
All the angles are measured w. r. t. tangential direction	

Numerically Centrifugal impeller with above specifications with 3mm thickness throughout the blade is shown in Fig. 1. A single passage of the impeller with inlet at 50mm ahead of the impeller and outlet at a distance of 35mm downstream of impeller is shown in Fig. 2. Casing is designed with a clearance of 0.7mm throughout the blade height. Three values of tip clearance, namely 2.2%, 5.1%, and 7.9% of rotor blade height at the exit of trailing edge blade height are obtained by moving the casing axially. Boundary layer clustering is done with four blocks around the blade for all models. Total pressure with boundary layer profile is used for inlet boundary condition and mass flow rate at outlet. Rotating frame of reference is given to the entire domain. ANSYS-CFX software is used for obtaining the solution and standard k- ϵ turbulence model is used for the closure. The centrifugal compressors of three tip clearances were analysed at four different flow coefficients.

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of centrifugal compressor setup

Fig. 2. Details of Configurations Tested

Fig. 3. Centrifugal compressor without and with partial shroud

2.1. MODELING OF COMPRESSOR BLADES:

Based on public domain literature on design of compressor blades used in aero engines, typical blade profile is constructed using the template based software module built in ANSYS workbench-16 version. The blade gen layout with construction features related to wrapper angle, number of blades, angles distribution and blade thickness for generation of three dimensional blades was done as shown Figure-3 in order to carry out structural analysis of the blade surfaces the software provided export options to generate computational mesh accounting blade thickness is also explored in static structural analysis package. The blade profiles generated in above software module are imported to template based multi-block structured computational mesh software module called turbo grid. The information related to machine data, profile curves, several inputs required for width factor periodicity production, topology freezing for generation of geometric representation in terms of surface mesh generation with master and slave control points being generated, default orientation of master and slave control points on the blade surfaces are to be moved to obtain better orthogonally between mesh points. After these operations three dimensional computational mesh generation process for compressor blade with boundary patches, periodic surfaces are created.

2.2. MESHING OF COMPRESSOR BLADES:

The three dimensional mesh generated for compressor blade is imported into the ANSYS Pre-processor using Turbo setup. In this process the grid data is read and checked for right handed coordinate system and scaling the grid data into SI units, domain setup with material properties required are highlighted. The surface mesh of blade inlet, exit, blade, left and right periodic and hub and shroud surfaces are visualized. The compressor impeller with multiple blades in shaded view is shown in Figure-4. The blade geometry designed has been saved as bgd file for future modifications and shape optimization. For further analysis, the bgd file can be exported as hub, shroud, profile and periodic curves to Turbo grid module where space discretization can be carried out which in turn can be exported to CFD flow simulation. In addition to this, this software also exports as IGES file for discretization of computational mesh with structured multi block mesh for blade thickness for structural analysis. Thus for rapid analysis, this software module provides detailed 3D solid modeling geometry components for maximum accuracy when assessing a particular design. The control points on the periodic line should be positioned, e.g. in the middle of the blade passage. Selecting the options-show-duplicate blade option will give guidance to locate the mid passage points. After the modifications to control points to improve minimum face angles and selecting the mesh size options the resulting topology for blade hub and shroud surfaces where in it is observed that percentage of bad elements is zero. The Volume mesh has been generated. The mesh quality in terms of skew angles, aspect ratio and right-handedness was checked and the grid data was found to be within tolerances. The mesh has been exported as gtm file for further pre-processing in the ANSYS - CFD pre and solver software package.

Figure-4. Surface grid single Blade, Shaded view of 3D compressor blades.

2.3. FLOW SIMULATION IN CENTRIFUGAL COMPRESSOR BLADE:

The three dimensional mesh generated for compressor blade is imported into the ANSYS Pre-processor using Turbo setup. In this process the grid data is read and checked for right handed coordinate system and scaling the grid data into SI units. Among several boundary conditions applied for flow simulation blade wall rotation about Z-axis with specified revolution per minute is accounted. The boundary

conditions determine to a large extent the characteristics of the solution you obtain. Therefore, it is important to set boundary conditions that accurately reflect the real situation to allow you to obtain accurate results.

Figure-5. Boundary conditions (Flow Solver).

For a given computational domain, boundary conditions can be given that over-specify or under-specify the problem. This usually results in non-physical solutions or failure of the solution to converge. After completion of flow simulation a macro built in the software for generations of report is activated to obtain performance and efficiency calculations. The variations in the rotational speed of the blade has been accounted to predict total pressure ratio and Isentropic efficiency of the blade is estimated and plots generated to understand the phenomena of choking and surging. The influence of pressure loading on the blades for structural integrity is examined using linear static structural analysis module built in ANSYS workbench. The process of taking blade geometry in structural simulation is connected first and later CFX result file was imported. Setup is activated so as to obtain the geometry of the blade along with fluid-solid surfaces in structural simulation module. Automatic methods to generate computational mesh for blade along with thickness are used and applied to get imported pressure load on blade surface. Blade is constrained through fixed support and using inertial option wall rotations are defined. With this physics setup and material properties simulations has been carried out for Total displacement and equivalent stresses. The results obtained for blade deformations and maximum and minimum stress levels are interpreted graphically

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS:

Blade Loading: The impellor blades are rotating with 2000 rpm is subjected to mass flow 0.087 kg/s/vane with the working pressure is of order 1 atm. The pressure loading over stream wise directions for 2.2% tip clearance at with and without partial shroud at different flow coefficients are shown in the Figures 6 -7. The pressure profiles on the surfaces near hub mean and tip region provides details of boundary layer separation with steep adverse pressure gradients. Fluid flow without PS and with PS on tip of the blade, significant change in pressure on suction side is observed. Low static pressure on suction and high pressure on pressure side of the blade is observed. With increase in tip clearance, static pressure on both pressure side and suction side are reducing.

Fig. 6 Blade loading for 2.2% clearance at with and without partial shroud at flow coefficient 0.12

Fig. 7. Blade loading for 2.2% clearance at with and without partial shroud at flow coefficient 0.34.

Radial Velocity and Impeller total efficiency: A comparison of the circumferentially averaged radial velocity distributions from the hub to the shroud at the impeller exit is plotted in Figure 8. At the impeller exit, the flow near the shroud experiences secondary flows that block the flow passage. In addition, the tip clearance flow influences the secondary flow structure and further blocks the flow passage, thereby generating a large total pressure loss near the shroud. The blockage resulted in a rapid decrease in the radial velocity near the shroud. The low radial velocity near the shroud indicated a separated zone in which a high loss fluid accumulated. A blocked zone with a negative radial velocity was present above 98% span from the hub, suggesting that a strong reverse flow was present near the shroud because low momentum flow could not overcome the pressure gradient in the radial direction. Figure show the efficiency curve features of typical centrifugal compressors, where efficiency peak at a certain flow rate. Increasing or decreasing the flow rate from this optimum point results in a reduction in efficiency.

Fig. 8 Radial Velocity from hub to shroud at flow coefficient 0.14

Figure-9. Impeller total efficiency to normalized mass flow rate

Work input coefficient: The performance of a centrifugal compressor is significantly affected by tip clearance in two ways. First, tip leakage flow causes large pressure losses due to mixing with the main passage flow. Second, the impeller cannot transfer its momentum to the fluid across the tip clearance, which decreases the total work input. Consequently, small changes in the tip clearance could have large influences on the compressor performance. The work input coefficient to the impeller exit is shown in Figure 10. Higher work input coefficients were associated with all impellers with tip clearances smaller than that of the original case. Additionally, decreasing the tip clearance at the trailing edge rather than at the leading edge effectively increased the work input. The shapes of the total efficiency curves for all cases resembled the original case, with a maximum peak as shown in Figure 11. The impellers with reduced tip clearances yielded better efficiencies because the mixing loss caused by the tip clearance flow was reduced. At low mass flow rates, the total efficiency difference between 2.2% and 7.9% decreased compared to the peak-efficiency point, probably because the mixing loss due to the tip clearance was less prominent.

Figure 10 Work input coefficient to the impeller exit

Tangential velocity distribution at Exit: Circumferentially tangential velocity distribution from hub to casing at outlet is shown in fig. 12. The tangential velocity is minimum near hub and casing indicating the boundary layer. The maximum tangential velocity is observed near the casing, indicating higher energy transfer near casing. However, the peak in tangential velocity moves away from the casing as the tip clearance increases. Also the peak moves away from the casing as the flow coefficient decreases. At $\phi=0.28$, the tangential velocity peak is moving away from casing as tip clearance is increasing and the peak of 5% clearance is near the 60% span from hub. The minimum tip clearance at $\phi=0.28$ is showing a low tangential velocity as the mass flow rate falling beyond operating range. At $\phi=0.34$, the tangential velocity is minimum is

observed near hub and casing. The tangential velocity is increasing with decreasing clearance up to one third of the span and then it is decreasing with decrease in clearance. The minimum tangential velocity at hub is increasing with flow coefficient increase, whereas tangential velocity at casing is decreasing with flow coefficient increase at slower rate. Also tangential velocity is decreasing with flow coefficient increase.

Fig.11 Tangential velocity distribution from hub to casing at outlet

Pressure Ratio at Off Design Conditions:

Outlet to inlet pressure ratio at different flow coefficients is shown in fig. 12. Increase in pressure ratio with the partial shroud on tip of the blade is observed at all flow coefficients. But with 2.2% tip clearance on the tip of the blade shown increase in pressure ratio is observed at all flow coefficients because of more fluid leakage through the without partial shroud.

Fig. 12 Pressure ratio for different flow coefficients

Relative Velocity Vectors in Meridional Planes:

Relative velocity vectors component on the plane for four flow coefficients $\phi = 0.12, 0.18, 0.28$ and 0.34 at tip clearance $\tau = 2.2\%$, are shown in Figures 13 to 16 respectively. At $\phi = 0.12$, the relative velocities are more near the suction side shroud corner and relative velocity is low near pressure side hub corner. Due to the centrifugal forces and curvature, velocity on suction side is higher than pressure side. For other tip clearances, leakage of flow from pressure side to suction side of the blade through the tip gap is observed. Vertical flow near the suction side of the blade meets the tip leakage flow near suction side shroud corner. At $\phi = 0.28$, circulating flow near the suction surface is observed due the strong centrifugal forces. For other tip clearances, wake growth is altering the flow pattern. At higher tip clearances, increase in leakage flow observed. At $\phi = 0.34$, downstream of the impeller, absence of centrifugal force causes the flow nearly uniform. However the passage wake is still observable at this plane. At the trailing edge of the blade velocity difference on pressure and suction sides is observed with jet and wake flow.

Fig. 13. Velocity vectors at turbo surface 1.8 of the blade with and without partial shroud at 2.2% tip clearance for flow coefficient 0.12

Fig. 14. Velocity vectors at turbo surface 1.8 of the blade with and without partial shroud at 2.2% tip clearance for flow coefficient 0.18.

Fig. 15. Velocity vectors at turbo surface 1.8 of the blade with and without partial shroud at 2.2% tip clearance for flow coefficient 0.28.

Fig. 16. Velocity vectors at turbo surface 1.8 of the blade with and without partial shroud at 2.2% tip clearance for flow coefficient 0.34.

4. CONCLUSIONS:

Tip clearance effects in a centrifugal compressor impeller with three different values of tip clearances i.e., $\tau = 2.2\%$, 5.1% and 7.9% are examined at four flow coefficients $\phi = 0.12, 0.18, 0.28$ and 0.34 . The effect of tip clearance on total impeller efficiency, work input coefficient, tangential velocity and radial velocity from inlet to outlet of the compressor are analyzed. Tangential velocity graphs at the outlet of the compressor show that with increase in tip clearance the losses increase. The relative velocity vectors show that there is a shifting of low momentum fluid from suction surface to pressure surface in tip clearance region due to tip leakage flow. Wake region near suction side shroud corner is observed. Wake region growth and movement towards the mid pitch with increase in clearance is observed. It is observed that maximum stress is taking place at the hub surface trailing edge and minimum stress is noticed on shroud surface when pressure load obtained from CFD solution is specified on the blade surfaces is shown in Figure-17. As mass flow varies at constant rotational speeds the magnitude of maxima and minima of stresses decrease. Similarly, the total deformation also decreases at constant speed at different mass flow rates.

Figure-17. Pressure contour blade suction side and Pressure contour blade pressure side

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